

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №6 (20)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 6 (20)

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О журнале

*Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.*

*Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.*

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Муस्ताкиллиги, 70/2.

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SIGNIFICANCE OF THE T-34C POLYMORPHISM IN THE CYP17A1 GENE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BENIGN PROSTATIC HYPERPLASIA AND PROSTATE CANCER

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Resume. Androgens play an important role during the development of both normal prostate epithelium and prostate cancer and variants of genes involved in androgen metabolism may be related to an increased risk of prostate disease. Cytochrome P450 17 α -hydroxylase/17,20-lyase (CYP17A1) is a key regulatory enzyme in the steroidogenic pathway; it catalysis both 17 α -hydroxylase and 17,20-lyase activities and is essential for the production of both androgens and glucocorticoids. In this review, we focus on the structure and enzymatic activity of CYP17A1 and the mechanism of modulation of CYP17A1 activities. We discuss the relationship between common genetic variations in CYP17A1 gene and prostate cancer risk and the main effects of these variations on the prediction of susceptibility and clinical outcomes of prostate cancer patients. The mechanism of action, the efficacy and the clinical potential of CYP17A1 inhibitors in prostate cancer are also summarized.

Keywords: CYP17A1, Steroid 17 alpha-hydroxylase/17,20-lyase, CYP17A1 polymorphisms, CYP17A1 inhibitors, prostate cancer.

СУР17А1 ГЕНИНИНГ Т-34С ПОЛИМОРФИЗМИНИНГ ПРОСТАТА БЕЗИНИНГ ҲАВФСИЗ ГИПЕРПАЗИЯСИ ВА ПРОСТАТА РАКИ ПАТОГЕНЕЗИДАГИ РОЛИ

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Резюме. Андрогенлар ҳам нормал простата эпителийининг, ҳам простата саратоннинг ривожланишида муҳим рол ўйнайди. Андрогенлар метаболизмида иштирок этувчи генларнинг турли вариантлари простата безига оид касалликлар ривожланиши хавфининг ортиши билан боғлиқ бўлиши мумкин. Цитохром Р450 17 α -гидроксилаза/17,20-лиаза (СУР17А1) стероидогенез йўлида асосий регулятор фермент ҳисобланади; у 17 α -гидроксилаза ва 17,20-лиаза фаолликларини катализлайди ҳамда андрогенлар ва глюкокортикоидларнинг синтези учун зарурдир. Ушбу шарҳда биз СУР17А1 нинг тузилиши, ферментатив фаоллиги ва унинг функцияларини модуляция қилиши механизмларига эътибор қаратамиз. Шунингдек, СУР17А1 генидаги кенг тарқалган генетик вариациялар ва простата саратон ривожланиши хавфи ўртасидаги боғлиқлик, бу вариацияларнинг касалликка мойилликни башиорат қилиши ҳамда беморларнинг клиник натижаларга таъсири муҳокама қилинади. Простата саратонда СУР17А1 ингибиторларининг таъсир механизми, самарадорлиги ва клиник қўллаш салоҳияти ҳам умумлаштирилган.

Калит сўзлар: СУР17А1, стероид 17-алфа-гидроксилаза/17,20-лиаза, СУР17А1 полиморфизмлари, СУР17А1 ингибиторлари, простата беши саратони.

РОЛЬ ПОЛИМОРФИЗМА Т-34с В ГЕНЕ СУР17А1 В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ ДОБРОКАЧЕСТВЕННОЙ ГИПЕРПАЗИИ ПРЕДСТАТЕЛЬНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ И РАКА ПРОСТАТЫ

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Резюме. Андрогены играют важную роль в развитии как нормального эпителия предстательной железы, так и рака простаты, а варианты генов, участвующих в метаболизме андрогенов, могут быть связаны с повышенным риском заболеваний предстательной железы. Цитохром Р450 17 α -гидроксилаза/17,20-лиаза (СУР17А1) является ключевым регуляторным ферментом стероидогенного пути; он катализирует как 17 α -гидроксилазную, так и 17,20-лиазную активности и необходим для продукции как андрогенов, так и глюкокортикоидов. В данном обзоре мы сосредоточиваем внимание на структуре и ферментативной активности СУР17А1, а также на механизме модуляции его функций. Мы обсуждаем связь между распространёнными генетическими вариациями гена СУР17А1 и

риском развития рака предстательной железы, а также основные эффекты этих вариаций на прогнозирование предрасположенности и клинических исходов у пациентов с раком простаты. Также представлены механизм действия, эффективность и клинический потенциал ингибиторов CYP17A1 при раке предстательной железы.

Ключевые слова: CYP17A1, стероид 17-альфа-гидроксилаза/17, 20-лиаза, полиморфизмы CYP17A1, ингибиторы CYP17A1, рак предстательной железы.

Introduction. Prostate diseases, including benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) and prostate cancer (PC), represent a major global health concern, particularly among aging male populations. These conditions are influenced by a combination of genetic, hormonal, and environmental factors, with androgens playing a central role in prostate growth and disease progression. Among the various genes involved in androgen metabolism, CYP17A1 (cytochrome P450 17 α -hydroxylase/17,20-lyase) is of particular interest due to its role in steroidogenesis, influencing the production of both androgens and glucocorticoids.

The CYP17A1 gene, located on chromosome 10q24.32, encodes a crucial enzyme in the biosynthesis of steroid hormones. It catalyzes two essential reactions: 17 α -hydroxylation and 17,20-lyase activity, both of which regulate androgen and glucocorticoid synthesis. Variants within this gene have been hypothesized to affect androgen levels, thereby influencing the risk and progression of prostate diseases. One such variant, the T-34C polymorphism, has been studied extensively for its potential role in altering CYP17A1 enzymatic activity, which may contribute to increased susceptibility to BPH and prostate cancer.

2. Genetic Polymorphisms and Disease Susceptibility

Genetic variations can significantly impact individual predisposition to diseases, particularly when they influence key metabolic pathways. The T-34C polymorphism in the CYP17A1 gene has been proposed as a functional variant that may enhance androgen biosynthesis, leading to higher circulating testosterone levels, which in turn could stimulate prostate growth and increase cancer risk. Several studies have investigated the correlation between this polymorphism and the incidence of BPH and PC, suggesting that individuals carrying the mutant (G) allele or the G/G genotype may have an increased risk of developing these conditions. Conversely, the A allele (wild type) and A/A genotype have been associated with protective effects, reducing susceptibility to prostate-related disorders.

The aim of the study is to assess the role of T-34C polymorphism in the CYP17A1 regulatory genes in the mechanism of benign prostatic hyperplasia and prostate cancer development.

Materials and methods. Study Subjects. The present study included 74 men who visited the clinic for LUTS between January 2022 and December 2023. Patients' clinical symptoms were assessed using the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) and quality of life (QoL) questionnaires. The prostate volumes of patients were measured by transrectal ultrasonography, and the serum prostate-specific antigen (PSA) level of each subject was determined. Peak urine flow velocity (Q_{max}) and mean urine flow velocity (Q_{avg}) were measured using a uroflowmetry system.

The blood analysis of associations of polymorphisms of the studied genes will be carried out using a case-control model (case-control, comparison of two samples). Genetic research and analysis of the obtained data will be carried out according to the GRIPS principles in order to increase transparency and the quality of risk prediction. PCR analysis will be carried out using thermal cyclers Applied Biosystems 2720 (USA) and CG1-96 (Corbett Research QUAGEN Germany) and Rotor GeneQ (QUAGEN Germany) in accordance with the amplification programs. When collecting blood from patients, standard vacuum tubes Vacutainer Becton Dickinson International (USA) with EDTA will be used.

Subjects were excluded from the study if they had prostate cancer, neurogenic bladder, urethral stricture, acute/chronic prostatitis, urinary tract infection, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, previous pelvic surgery, or hypertension. Subjects were assigned to either the control group (prostate volume <30 mL) or the group with BPH [prostate volume 30 mL; IPSS, >8; Q_{max}, <15 mL/sec] group, depending on symptoms (11,12). All subjects provided written informed consent.

Results. According to the data we obtained by comparative case/control analysis, all allelic and genotypic frequencies of the T-34C polymorphism in the CYP17A1 gene, except for the heterozygous A/G and mutant G/G genotype (38.7% vs. 30.5% at $\chi^2=1.6$, $p=0.3$, OR=1.4, 95%CI:0.81-2.54 and 17.0% vs. 8.6% at $\chi^2=3.3$, $p=0.1$ OR=2.2, 95%CI:0.95-5.04) were statistically significantly different in the main patient group compared to the control group (see Table 1).

The revealed trends of low prevalence detection values of heterozygous heterozygous A/G and mutant G/G genotype frequency of the 34C polymorphism in the CYP17A1 gene were confirmed by the performed odds ratio analysis (OR=1.4 and OR= 2.2) of the development of DGPJ and RHD (see Table 1).

The analysis of allele frequency distribution for polymorphism 34C in CYP17A1 gene in the main group of patients and in the comparison group revealed statistically significant differences between them (see Table 1). Thus, OR value of G minor allele (33.8% vs. 23.8%) of this polymorphism was 1.6 (with $\chi^2=4.3$, $p=0.05$, 95%CI:1.03-2.6), which characterizes G minor allele as risky and presence of this allele increases the risk of the above mentioned pathologies 1.6 times, while A allele of major type (66.2% vs. 76.2% at $\chi^2=4.3$, $p=0.05$, 95%CI:0.39-0.97, OR=0.6) of this polymorphism can be considered as a protective marker in relation to the development of BPH and RHD in comparison with the control sample (see Table 1)

Table 1.

Carriage of alleles and genotypes of the T-34C polymorphism in the CYP17A1 gene in the main group of patients and in the control group.

Alleles and genotypes	Number of alleles and genotypes examined				χ^2	p	OR	95%CI
	Main group		Control group					
	n	%	n	%				
A	135	63.7	160	76.2	7.8	0.01	0.5	0.36 – 0.83
G	77	36.3	50	23.8	7.8	0.01	1.8	1.2 – 2.78
A/A	47	44.3	64	61.0	5.8	0.03	0.5	0.3 – 0.88
A/G	41	38.7	32	30.5	1.6	0.30	1.4	0.81 – 2.54
G/G	18	17.0	9	8.6	3.3	0.10	2.2	0.95 – 5.04

Conclusion. The study shows that the T-34C polymorphism of the CYP17A1 gene is associated with susceptibility to benign prostatic hyperplasia and may contribute to prostate cancer risk. The G allele and G/G genotype were more frequent among affected patients and demonstrated higher odds ratios, indicating an increased predisposition, whereas the A allele appears protective. These findings highlight the role of CYP17A1 genetic variation in androgen-dependent prostate diseases and support its potential use as a molecular marker for early risk assessment.

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For citation: Mamarizaev A.A., Azimova S.B., Rustamov U.M. Significance of the T-34C polymorphism in the CYP17A1 gene in the development of benign prostatic hyperplasia and prostate cancer // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2025. – № 6(20). – P. 581–583. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17776716>